

Modeling Depression in Preclinical Research: A Comprehensive Review of Induction Models

Gauri Pamod Gawande^{1*}, Smeeta Sudhir Sadar², Niraj Sudhakar Vyawahare³, Ajay Vilas Lokhande⁴,
Dhanashri Prakash Sonavane⁵

¹Research Scholar, Department of Pharmacology, Dr. D. Y. Patil College of Pharmacy, Akurdi, Pune-411044, Maharashtra, India

²Associate Professor, Department of Pharmacology, Dr. D. Y. Patil College of Pharmacy, Akurdi, Pune-411044, Maharashtra, India

³Principal, Department of Pharmacology, Dr. D. Y. Patil College of Pharmacy, Akurdi, Pune-411044, Maharashtra, India

⁴Research Scholar, Department of Pharmacology, Dr. D. Y. Patil College of Pharmacy, Akurdi, Pune-411044, Maharashtra, India

⁵Research Scholar, Department of Pharmacology, Dr. D. Y. Patil College of Pharmacy, Akurdi, Pune-411044, Maharashtra, India

*Corresponding Author Email: gauripgawande28@gmail.com

Abstract: Depression is a complex mental health disorder include sadness, loss of interest in regular activities and other cognitive, emotional and physical symptoms. It is a leading global health concern, affecting all age groups and contributing significantly to disability, suicide rates and economic burden. It affects mood, thinking and behaviour often leading to fatigue, sleep disturbances, changes in appetite and difficulty in concentration. Depression is a comorbidity associated with polycystic ovary syndrome, chrohn's , diabetes, pregnancy and stress. There are various mechanisms which causes depression. The most common mechanism is imbalance in neurotransmitters like serotonin and dopamine. This review include stress, menopause, prenatal hypertension, maternal separation, surgically induced, stress, learned helplessness models of depression. Larger number of population is unaware about different causes of depression. So this review will be helpful in terms of awaring researchers about various induction models of depression. Therefore, induction of depression and its mechanisms needs to be understand thoroughly. Pathology of depression can be study using different animal models. Hence in this review, various mechanisms which are involved in the pathogenesis of depression are included and various experimental depression models used in preclinical studies have been demonstrated. This will be helpful for the researcher for evaluation of new drug entity and drug repurposing.

Keywords: Depression, Animal models, Comorbidity, Induction models, Preclinical study

1. INTRODUCTION

In worldwide depression is fourth leading morbidity increases significantly and affecting individual mental as well as physical well-being. India is one of the leading country shows maximum depression. It is a condition with persistent feeling of sadness, low mood and loss of interest in various activities for at least two weeks causing significant impairment of daily life [1]. Low confidence, poor concentration, appetite change, fatigue, sleeping too much or insomnia, weight gain or weight loss, low energy and in severe condition suicidal thoughts are common symptoms of Depression [2,3].

According to WHO, 320 million people are affected by depression worldwide [4]. After COVID-19 pandemic it has been reported that most of the population are affected by depression [5]. It affects emotions, thoughts and physical well-being and leads to the impairment in daily life. Psychological stress, trauma, environmental, genetic and biochemical factors contribute to depression [6]. Physical exam questionnaire, thyroid test, psychiatric evaluation, diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorder is used to evaluate depression. Major depressive disorder is one of the major type of depression worldwide. Common mechanism to explain pathology of depression include monoamine hypothesis. In this case, there is monoamine neurotransmitters including serotonin (5-HT), norepinephrine (NE) and dopamine (DA) which regulate mood and energy levels. Its depletion results into psychological disorder like depression.

Depression have high comorbidity in PCOS, hypertension, crohn's disease and diabetes. Some studies have shown that depression is occurs more commonly during pregnancy, pre-natal and post-natal. In case of PCOS, decrease in level of estrogen and progesterone level cause depletion in serotonin which causes depression. Hypertension causes decrease in the brain derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) level which leads to depression [76]. Crohn's disease causes increase in pro-inflammatory cytokines like IL-6, IL-1 β and NO in the brain which is responsible to cause depression. Diabetes causes depression due to reduce in BDNF concentration. Animal models plays crucial role for understanding the pathogenesis followed by depression which is similar in humans and animals. Animal models resemble same symptoms observed in individuals affecting depression. This review emphasize on principle and various study procedures for chemically induced, surgically induced and disease related preclinical models. The aim of this review is to highlight their role in research and identify potential areas for improvement.

1.1 Status of Current Animal Models of Depression

While studying an animal models of depression or any other disease, the goals of that model should be clear [7]. The animal models are always based on theory. In case of depression, the animal model should replicate symptoms and etiological factors that cause depression in humans. These models explore for possible medications. It is widely used to study the mechanism followed by the treatment of symptoms. The animal models listed below are used for the anti-depressant study [8]. Though animal models do not completely resemble human depression, most animal models are relevant as they mimic many features observed in human situation. It serves as a powerful tool for the study of etiology, pathogenesis and treatment of depression [9].

1.2 Limitations associated with Conventional Animal Models of Depression

Animal models are used to understand the depression and development of anti-depressant therapies. However there are several limitations which are associated with conventional animal models. Many animal models are fail to fully replicate human depression as it is complex [10]. Tail Suspension Test and Forced Swim Test are commonly used to induce depressive-like behaviours in rodents although some researches have shown that it may reflect stress coping mechanism and not depression [11]. While conducting chronic stress model, animals were exposed to unpredictable stressors which leads to inconsistent results due to variations in stress protocols [12]. It leads to variations in findings [13]. Though conventional animal models plays a wide role in depression, it has some limitations. So there is need to develop more sophisticated models that better to treat human depression.

2. PCOS INDUCED DEPRESSION

2.1 DHEA induced PCOS

Principle

PCOS is most common condition occur in women globally. Nowadays younger girls are at high risk of suffering from PCOS. It is an endocrine disorder associated with psychological symptoms including depression. Dehydroepiandrosterone (DHEA) is an endogenous steroid hormone present in the adrenal gland. It serves as a precursor to estrogen and androgen which play important role in PCOS [14]. Elevated levels of dehydroepiandrosterone (DHEA) results in elevated level of androgens which causes decrease in progesterone and estrogen. It results in imbalance of neurotransmitters like serotonin and dopamine which regulate mood. The low level of serotonin and dopamine causes depression [15].

Procedure

Female C57BL/6 mice (21 days age) divided into groups with free access of food and water. DHEA (6mg/100g b. wt) dissolved in sesame oil 0.1ml of sesame oil and injected by subcutaneous route for 20 days for induction of PCOS. Then behavioural tests like forced-swimming test, open field test and tail suspension test are performed for evaluation of anti-depressant activity [16]. Biochemical parameters like measurement of monoamines in hypothalamus and stratum are performed as it plays main role in depression [17,18].

2.2 Letrazole induced PCOS

Principle

This model gives idea about use of Letrazole for induction of PCOS [19]. Letrazole inhibits the enzyme aromatase which converts androgens (testosterone) into estrogen [20]. Reduced aromatase activity decreases estrogen levels and increases androgen levels i.e. hyperandrogenism [21]. Due to elevated androgen levels it inhibit follicular growth, form multiple cyst follicles and suppress ovulation which ultimately results into PCOS [22]. Decrease in estrogen result in decrease in level of serotonin and dopamine which are neurotransmitters responsible for regulation of mood. Its low concentration causes depression like behaviour.

Procedure

Female Wistar rats (120-150 g) divided into groups. Letrazole is given as induction orally with a dose of 1mg/kg for 21 days. After 20 days, Behavioral Tests like Open field test, Y-Maze test, Elevated plus maze test, Sucrose preference test are performed for confirmation of induction of depression. Determination of estrogen, androgen and serotonin is performed. At the end of the study histopathology of ovaries and hippocampus is carried out [23].

3. PRE-NATAL HYPERTENSION INDUCED DEPRESSION

Principle

Hypertension is one of the common disorder during pregnancy. Prenatal hypertension is induced using osmotic pumps which causes preeclampsia. Preeclampsia is a high blood pressure condition occurred during pregnancy [24,25,26]. The condition causes decrease in BDNF protein levels which results in depression.

Procedure

Pregnant Sprague dawley rats were kept for 7 days for acclimatization. Then animals were divided in separate cages. On gestational day 12, animals were anesthetized and mini-osmotic pumps were inserted intra-peritoneally. For induction of preeclampsia, osmotic pumps were loaded with tyrosine-1 kinase which causes hypertension by inhibiting vascular endothelial growth factor [27]. From

post-partum week 1 to 9, forced swimming test, elevated zero maze test and sucrose preference were performed for confirmation of depression [28,29]. Then inflammatory assays were performed using Interleukin-17 and BDNF which are responsible for depression [30].

4. MATERNAL SEPARATION INDUCED DEPRESSION

Principle

This model proposed maternal separation as a stressor to induce depression like behaviour in neonatal rats [31]. It is one of the widely used model for induction of depression in pregnancy. BDNF is a nerve growth factor. Its concentration is decreased in hippocampus during stress [32].

Procedure

Long-Evans hooded pregnant rats with gestational day 12 were housed in individual cages with 12:12 hour light: dark cycle and free access to food and water. On post-natal day (PND) 2, each litter was moved from their mother and arranged as 6 female and 2 male pups per cage. From PND 2 to PND 14, maternal separation is done by removing pups from home cage daily for 180 minutes. Locomotor activity was measured from PND 50 and 60 using forced swim test [33]. On PND 95, animals were killed by decapitation and BDNF levels were measured in brain. These pups were found to be hypoactive as compared to normal. Decrease in BDNF protein levels was found in hippocampus which is an indicator of depression [34].

5. DIABETES INDUCED DEPRESSION

5.1 Streptozotocin induced diabetes

Principle

Streptozotocin induced PCOS is a model which shows induction of diabetes in association of depression. Streptozotocin is an alkylating agent and naturally occurring antibiotic which is derived from bacteria *Streptomyces achromogenes* [35]. It enters pancreatic beta cells through GLUT2 transporter and induces DNA damage and cell death by alkylation and fragmentation. It results in decreased insulin production and hyperglycemia which results in diabetes [36,37]. It alters neurotransmitter release which causes depletion in serotonin and dopamine which ultimately causes depression.

Procedure

Young adult male mice with 3 months age are procured. They are housed as two animals in one cage with free access of water and food. The animals were allowed for acclimatization to new environment for 10 days before the start of the experiment. Two days prior the induction of diabetes, light dark test was performed to evaluate depression. Diabetic is induced by single intraperitoneal injection of streptozotocin given by dissolved in 0.1 N pH 4.5 citrate buffer. Body weight and glucose analysis is done on first day and last day of the study for confirmation of diabetes induction. Behavioral Tests are carried out. Histopathology of brain and ovaries are done at the end of the experiment [38].

5.2 Alloxan induced diabetes

Principle

Alloxan is a chemical compound widely used for induction of diabetes in laboratory animals. Brain- derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) plays an important role in pathophysiology of diabetes and depression [39]. BDNF plays a major role in functions of neuron [40]. The levels of BDNF is decreased in depression while in case of anti-depressants the levels of neurotrophin is increased [41]. This model shows induction of diabetes in laboratory animals along with depression.

Procedure

Male adult Wistar rats of 60 years old are housed in separate cages with free access of food and water. Alloxan induced diabetes more effectively in fasting state as increased blood glucose level shows partial protection [42]. Animals kept for 18 hours fasting before induction. Single intraperitoneal injection of alloxan dissolved in physiological salt solution (0.9% NaCl) is given at a dose of 150mg/kg. After 48 hours the animals showed hyperglycemia. Blood glucose level of animals were monitored daily. On last day, open field test, forced swimming test are performed to check depressive behaviour of animals. BDNF is measured to know the correlation between diabetes and depression [43].

6. SURGICALLY INDUCED DEPRESSION

Principle

This model mainly focus on surgically induced depression. In this case, ovariectomy is done by removal of ovaries. Ovary is responsible for release of estrogen which plays important role in mood, memory and mental state [44]. Depletion in estrogen results into depression like symptoms [45].

Procedure

Female mice aged 9 weeks were kept in separate cages with free access to water and food. Animals were kept for 7 days for acclimatization to new environment. First animals were anesthetized using sodium phenobarbital 65 mg/kg intraperitoneally. Then incision was made using scissors and forceps. Ligation is done around ovary and fallopian tube. Then ovaries were removed along with periovarian fast. Thereafter, suture was done. Immobility time was measured using forced swimming test [46].

6.1 Chronic Perfusion of rat Brain with DHEAS

Principle

This model gives basic idea about mechanically induced depression. DHEA is a neurosteroid which is synthesized from cholesterol in nervous system [47]. DHEA can modulate gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA) which lower concentration is related to depression [14]. DHEAS is a sulphate derivative of DHEA. It causes modulation in GABA mimetic system which plays a crucial role in mood regulation. Its alternation results into depression.

Procedure

Male Sprague-Dawley rats were kept as two per cages with free access of food and water. Rats were anesthetized with 0.5ml ketamine and xylazine in 2:1 ratio and placed on stereotaxic apparatus. Then a hole is drilled through their skull as per the stereotaxic coordinates. Then dehydroepiandrosterone sulphate (DHEAS) was inserted using 30 G cannula in the brain. Then immobility time is measured using forced swimming test for confirmation of depression. Then rats were anesthetized and trypan blue was injected as 1 μ l through cannula into brain. Rats were killed using decapitation and brains were removed. The levels of GABA is measured as it plays a major role in depression [48].

6.2 Bilateral Olfactory bulbectomy induced depression

Principle

Bilateral olfactory bulbectomy induced depression is an animal model which include olfactory bulbectomy for the induction of depression. Olfactory system is the part of limbic region which include hippocampus and amygdala [49]. These are responsible for emotions and memory. In case of olfactory bulbectomy, it affects hippocampal-amygdala circuit which affect neurotransmitters like noradrenaline, serotonin and glutamate [50]. It results in depression like behaviour.

Procedure

Male Sprague-Dawley rats weight 200-250 g were housed in separate cages with free access to food and water. Animals are kept for acclimatization for 7 days. Animals were anaesthetized with 2.5% w/v solution of tribromoethanol administered intraperitoneally. The head of the animal was shaved and then a midline incision was made. Then 2 mm of diameter 2 holes were drilled in the skull and removed olfactory bulbs using suction. Then the wound was closed. Thus, bilateral olfactory bulbectomy is done. After 14 days, behavioral tests like elevated plus maze test and open field test was performed [51]. Then biochemical parameters like concentration of noradrenaline, serotonin and glutamate was measured. These are necessary to conform the induction of depression [52,53].

7. MISCELLANEOUS

7.1 Stress induced depression

Principle

Stress is one of the important factor in depression. Chronic stress and prolonged stressful life responsible for the development of depressive behaviours [54,55,56]. It cause reduced size of hippocampus which is responsible for mood regulation in animals and humans. This shows link between stress and depressive symptoms [57]. It also causes alternation in neurotransmitter release like serotonin and dopamine which results in depression. Forced swimming test is most popular stress-based preclinical models of depression [58]. It include forced swimming as stressor. It require only limited time for induction [59].

Procedure

Wistar rats weighing 200g divided into group. In this model, the rodents are placed into a cylinder filled with cold water and are forced to swim to survive from an inescapable situation. Animals were initially given 15 minute training and then after 24 hours 6 minute testing session was given. After the treatment, Stressor i.e. forced swimming is given to the animals for 4 minutes. Duration of immobility and counts of immobility is recorded [38]. At the end of the study, histopathology is done. Increased immobility and counts immobility is a factor to measure depressive symptoms [60].

7.2 Reserpine induced depression

Principle

Epinephrine, serotonin and dopamine are brain monoamines. These neurotransmitters plays important role in pathophysiology of depression and its deficiency causes depression [61]. Reserpine inhibit vesicular monoamine transporter irreversibly which is responsible for regular accumulation of monoamines into synaptic vesicles and reuptake into synapse. It inhibits pre-synaptic reuptake and storage which leads to depletion in monoamines like serotonin and dopamine and leads to depression [62]. Thus reserpine is widely used for induction of depression in animal models [63,64].

Procedure

Male Wistar rats (120- 150g) were obtained and housed under standard laboratory conditions (temperature 25°C with a 12-h light/dark cycle). Animals were divided in separate cages and allowed to acclimatize for 10 days to new environment. Reserpine was diluted in glacial acetic acid to a final concentration of 0.5% acetic acid in distilled water. Depression is induced to animals by intraperitoneal administration of reserpine at a dose of 0.5 mg/kg for 14 consecutive days. On day 1 and day 24 locomotor activity using forced swimming test was measured. On day 14, concentration of brain monoamines, hippocampal biochemical changes were measured [65].

7.3 Learned helplessness model of depression

Principle

Feeling of helplessness and try to give up in stressful condition is a major symptom in depression. The mechanism of Learned helplessness model is linked to the reduced in concentration of norepinephrine in brain [66]. This model include mild electric shock for the induction of depression. It results in behavioral changes including reduced aggression, reduced food and water intake, reduced social dominance, reduced preference for sweet tastes, anxiety and depression.

Procedure

Wistar rats are housed in separate cages. Inescapable electric foot shock was given to the animals for induction of Learned helplessness [67]. First trial was given with unavoidable electric shock. After 24 hours, the shock was delivered for 3 seconds separately to each animal for 3 consecutive days. This cycle is repeated 30 times per day with half minute interval. Animals are allowed to escape through an exit to neighbouring safe place. Animals are observed not to escape rather accept the stressor. In this model, depression is measured in terms of number of escape failure, passive avoidance and reduced locomotor activity [68,69,70].

8. CONCLUSION

This Review shows induction of Depression in various diseases followed by different mechanisms. By using this study, we can evaluate various preclinical models to study depression and cognitive impairment on laboratory animals. It is associated with impaired neurogenesis in hypothalamus, increased oxidative stress and increase pro-inflammatory factors. It gives an idea about various chemical induced, stress, prenatal and surgically induced depression models.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors would like to thank the Department of Pharmacology, Dr. D. Y. Patil College of Pharmacy, for providing all the facilities for doing this work.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Bathla, M. Singh, and P. Relan, "Prevalence of anxiety and depressive symptoms among patients with hypothyroidism," *Indian Journal of Endocrinology and Metabolism*, vol. 20, no. 4, pp. 468–474, 2016. doi: 10.4103/2230-8210.183476.
- [2] M. Becker, A. Pinhasov, and A. Ornoy, "Animal models of depression: What can they teach us about the human disease?," *Diagnostics*, vol. 11, no. 1, p. 123, 2021. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/diagnostics11010123>.
- [3] S. Yasugaki, H. Okamura, A. Kaneko, and Y. Hayashi, "Bidirectional relationship between sleep and depression," *Neuroscience Research*, vol. 211, pp. 57–64, Feb. 2025. doi: 10.1016/j.neures.2023.04.006.
- [4] L. Geftman, "Mental health 2024 statistics," *Laura Geftman Blog*, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.laurageftman.com/blog/mental-health-2024-statistics>
- [5] H. A. Cruz, R. D. Buenaventura, and M. P. V. Mariano, "Incidence of depressive and anxiety symptoms among elderly Filipinos during the COVID-19 pandemic: a descriptive cross-sectional study," *International Journal of Neuropsychopharmacology*, vol. 28, Suppl 1, p. i333, Feb. 2025. doi: 10.1093/ijnp/pyae059.594.
- [6] B. S. McEwen, "Non-genomic and genomic effects of steroids on neural activity," *Trends in Pharmacological Sciences*, vol. 12, pp. 141–147, 1991. doi: 10.1016/0165-6147(91)90531.
- [7] S. Paykel, "Basic concepts of depression," *Dialogues in Clinical Neuroscience*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 279–289, 2008. doi: <https://doi.org/10.31887/DCNS.2008.10.3/espaykel>.
- [8] E. J. Nestler, E. Gould, H. Manji, M. Bucan, R. S. Duman, H. K. Gershenfeld, *et al.*, "Preclinical models: Status of basic research in depression," *Neuroscience and Biobehavioral Reviews*, vol. 44, pp. 122–139, 2002. doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0006-3223\(02\)01405-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0006-3223(02)01405-1).
- [9] A. Shah, *American Psychiatric Association Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders*. Arlington, VA: American Psychiatric Publishing, 2013.
- [10] C. Slaney, J. Hinchcliffe, and E. Robinson, "Translational shifts in preclinical models of depression: implications for biomarkers for improved treatments," *PubMed*, 2023. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/7854-2018-44>.
- [11] Y. Hao, H. Ge, M. Sun, and Y. Gao, "Selecting an appropriate animal model of depression," *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, vol. 20, no. 19, p. 4827, 2019. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms20194827>.
- [12] Q. Yu, S. Hao, H. Wang, X. Song, Q. Shen, and J. Kang, "Depression-like behavior in a dehydroepiandrosterone-induced mouse model of polycystic ovary syndrome," *Biology of Reproduction*, vol. 95, no. 4, p. 79–1, 2016. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1095/biolreprod.116.142117>.
- [13] E. Fuchs and G. Flugge, "Experimental animal models for the simulation of depression and anxiety," *Dialogues in Clinical Neuroscience*, vol. 8, no. 3, 2006. doi: <https://doi.org/10.31887/DCNS.2006.8.3/efuchs>.

- [14] D. Anderson, B. Solorzano, and R. McCartney, "The pathophysiology of polycystic ovary syndrome: focusing on hyperandrogenism, insulin resistance, and obesity," *Journal of Pediatric and Adolescent Gynecology*, vol. 27, no. 5, pp. 282–289, 2014. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pnpbp.2024.111013>.
- [15] A. Balıkcı, M. Erdem, U. Keskin, S. Zincir, M. Gulsun, F. Ozcelik, *et al.*, "Depression, anxiety, and anger in patients with polycystic ovary syndrome," *Nöro Psikiyatri Arşivi*, vol. 51, no. 4, p. 328, 2014. doi: 10.5152/npa.2014.6898.
- [16] E. Castren, V. Vooikar, and T. Rantamaki, "Role of neurotrophic factors in depression," *Current Opinion in Pharmacology*, vol. 7, pp. 18–21, 2007. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coph.2006.08.009>.
- [17] A. Dokras, S. Clifton, W. Futterweit, and R. Wild, "Increased risk for abnormal depression scores in women with polycystic ovary syndrome: a systematic review and meta-analysis," *Obstetrics and Gynecology*, vol. 117, no. 1, pp. 145–152, 2011. doi: 10.1097/AOG.0b013e318202b0a4.
- [18] D. Kimmel, S. Paster, J. Burstein, J. Stovring, and P. Cochran, "Cardiac disease and recurrent gastrointestinal bleeding: angiodyplasia with accompanying hypertrophic subaortic stenosis," *PubMed*, 1977. doi: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/305604..>
- [19] M. P. Dandekar, M. Tadas, S. Sathı, A. Janglı, A. S. Shaikh, S. N. Gajula, *et al.*, "Oxyberberine revokes letrozole-induced polycystic ovarian syndrome and depression-like behavior in female Sprague-Dawley rats," *European Journal of Pharmacology*, 2025. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejphar.2025.177613>.
- [20] H. Kafalı, M. Iriadam, I. Ozardalı, and N. Demir, "Letrozole-induced polycystic ovaries in the rat: a new model for cystic ovarian disease," *Archives of Medical Research*, vol. 35, no. 2, pp. 103–108, 2004. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.arcmed.2003.10.005>.
- [21] D. Klimczak, K. Szlendak-Sauer, and S. Radowicki, "Depression in relation to biochemical parameters and age in women with polycystic ovary syndrome," *European Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology and Reproductive Biology*, vol. 184, pp. 43–47, 2015. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejogrb.2014.10.028>.
- [22] R. A. Prough, B. J. Clark, and C. M. Klinge, "Novel mechanisms for DHEA action," *Journal of Molecular Endocrinology*, vol. 56, no. 3, pp. R139–R155, 2016. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1530/JME-16-0013>.
- [23] A. Haslan, N. Samsulrizal, N. Hashim, N. Zin, F. Shirazi, and Y. Goh, "*Ficus deltoidea* ameliorates biochemical, hormonal, and histomorphometric changes in letrozole-induced polycystic ovarian syndrome rats," *BMC Complementary Medicine and Therapies*, vol. 21, pp. 1–13, 2021. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12906-021-03452-6>.
- [24] V. Castagne, P. Moser, S. Roux, and R. Porsolt, "Rodent models of depression: Forced swim and tail suspension behavioral despair tests in rats and mice," *Current Protocols in Neuroscience*, vol. 49, pp. 5–8, 2011. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/0471141755.ph0508s49>.
- [25] S. Chapuis-de-Andrade, C. Moret-Tatay, T. De Paula, T. Irigaray, and I. Antonello, "Psychological factors and coping strategies in pregnancies complicated by hypertension: A cluster-analytic approach," *Journal of Affective Disorders*, vol. 296, pp. 89–94, 2022. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jad.2021.09.049>.
- [26] M. Lippmann, A. Bress, B. Nemeroff, M. Plotsky, and M. Monteggia, "Long-term behavioural and molecular alterations associated with maternal separation in rats," *European Journal of Neuroscience*, vol. 26, no. 10, pp. 2831–2840, 2007. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1460-9568.2007.05522.x>.
- [27] S. Gong and F. Deng, "Renin-angiotensin system: The underlying mechanisms and promising therapeutical target for depression and anxiety," *Frontiers in Immunology*, vol. 13, p. 1053136, 2023. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fimmu.2022.1053136>.
- [28] K. Wallace, C. Bean, T. Bowles, S. Spencer, W. Randle, P. Kyle, J. Shaffery, "Hypertension, anxiety, and blood-brain barrier permeability are increased in post-partum rats with a history of severe preeclampsia/hemolysis, elevated liver enzymes and low platelet syndrome," *Hypertension*, vol. 72, pp. 946–955, 2018. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1161/HYPERTENSIONAHA.118.11770>.
- [29] K. Wallace, T. Bowles, A. Griffin, R. Robinson, L. Solis, T. Railey, *et al.*, "Evidence of anxiety, depression and learning impairments following prenatal hypertension," *Behavioral Sciences*, vol. 12, no. 2, p. 53, 2022. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/bs12020053>.
- [30] I. Brusse, J. Duvekot, J. Jongerling, E. Steegers, and I. De Koning, "Impaired maternal cognitive functioning after pregnancies complicated by severe pre-eclampsia: A pilot case-control study," *Acta Obstetrica et Gynecologica Scandinavica*, vol. 87, pp. 408–412, 2008. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/00016340801915127>.
- [31] S. Hall, "Social deprivation of neonatal, adolescent, and adult rats has distinct neurochemical and behavioral consequences," *Critical Reviews in Neurobiology*, vol. 12, no. 1–2, pp. 129–162, 1998. doi: 10.1615/CritRevNeurobiol.v12.i1-2.50.
- [32] J. Anderson, K. Freedland, R. Clouse, and P. Lustman, "The prevalence of comorbid depression in adults with diabetes: a meta-analysis," *Diabetes Care*, vol. 24, no. 6, pp. 1069–1078, 2001. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2337/diacare.24.6.1069>.
- [33] H. Barksby, S. Lea, P. Preshaw, and J. Taylor, "The expanding family of interleukin-1 cytokines and their role in destructive inflammatory disorders," *Clinical and Experimental Immunology*, vol. 149, no. 2, pp. 217–225, 2007. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2249.2007.03441.x>.
- [34] Y. Ye, L. Chen, J. Xu, Q. Dai, X. Luo, N. Shan, and H. Qi, "Preeclampsia and its complications exacerbate development of postpartum depression: A retrospective cohort study," *BioMed Research International*, Article ID 6641510, 2021. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/6641510>.
- [35] U. Chauhan, Y. Farbood, J. Marshall, S. Halder, D. Armstrong, F. Tse, *et al.*, "P-079 YI The association between anxiety and depression and health-related quality of life in patients with inflammatory bowel disease (IBD)," *Inflammatory Bowel Diseases*, vol. 22, Suppl 1, p. S34, 2016. doi: 10.1097/01.MIB.0000480173.43285.d1.
- [36] B. Van, L. Stapersma, E. H. El, J. Henrichs, E. M. Szigethy, E. M. Utens, and J. C. Escher, "Effectiveness of disease-specific cognitive-behavioural therapy on depression, anxiety, quality of life and the clinical course of disease in adolescents with inflammatory bowel disease: study protocol of a multicentre randomised controlled trial (HAPPY IBD)," *BMJ Open Gastroenterology*, vol. 3, no. 1, p. e000071, 2016. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjgast-2015-000071>.
- [37] A. Haj-Mirzaian *et al.*, "Anxiety- and depressive-like behaviors are associated with altered hippocampal energy and inflammatory status in a mouse model of Crohn's disease," *Neuroscience*, vol. 366, pp. 124–137, 2017. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroscience.2017.10.023>.

- [38] I. P. Mendonça *et al.*, “Semaglutide attenuates anxious and depressive-like behaviors and reverses the cognitive impairment in a type 2 diabetes mellitus mouse model via the microbiota-gut-brain axis,” *Journal of Neuroimmune Pharmacology*, vol. 19, p. 36, 2024. doi: [10.1007/s11481-024-10142-w](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11481-024-10142-w).
- [39] B. R. Bhavnani and R. C. Strickler, “Menopausal hormone therapy,” *Journal of Obstetrics and Gynaecology Canada*, vol. 27, no. 2, pp. 137–162, 2005. doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1701-2163\(16\)30186-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1701-2163(16)30186-4).
- [40] B. R. Bhavnani and R. C. Strickler, “Menopausal hormone therapy,” *Journal of Obstetrics and Gynaecology Canada*, vol. 27, no. 2, pp. 137–162, 2005. doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1701-2163\(16\)30186-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1701-2163(16)30186-4).
- [41] R. S. Duman and L. M. Monteggia, “A neurotrophic model for stress-related mood disorders,” *Biological Psychiatry*, vol. 59, no. 12, pp. 1116–1127, 2006. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biopsych.2006.02.013>.
- [42] R. Genud *et al.*, “DHEA lessens depressive-like behavior via GABA-ergic modulation of the mesolimbic system,” *Neuropsychopharmacology*, vol. 34, no. 3, pp. 577–584, 2009. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/npp.2008.46>.
- [43] R. M. Lindsay, S. J. Wiegand, C. A. Altar, and P. S. DiStefano, “Neurotrophic factors: from molecule to man,” *Trends in Neurosciences*, vol. 17, pp. 182–190, 1994. doi: [10.1016/0166-2236\(94\)90099-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0166-2236(94)90099-X).
- [44] N. Bekku and H. Yoshimura, “Animal model of menopausal depressive-like state in female mice: prolongation of immobility time in the forced swimming test following ovariectomy,” *Psychopharmacology*, vol. 183, pp. 300–307, 2005. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00213-005-0179-0>.
- [45] T. Szkudelski, “The mechanism of alloxan and streptozotocin action in B cells of the rat pancreas,” *Physiological Research*, vol. 50, no. 6, pp. 537–546, 2001.
- [46] Y. Badawy, A. Spector, Z. Li, and R. Desai, “The risk of depression in the menopausal stages: a systematic review and meta-analysis,” *Journal of Affective Disorders*, 2024. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jad.2024.04.041>.
- [47] R. Martínez-Tellez, M. J. Gómez-Villalobos, and G. Flores, “Alteration in dendritic morphology of cortical neurons in rats with diabetes mellitus induced by streptozotocin,” *Brain Research*, vol. 1048, no. 1–2, pp. 108–115, 2005. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.brainres.2005.04.048>.
- [48] D. Taliaz *et al.*, “Resilience to chronic stress is mediated by hippocampal brain-derived neurotrophic factor,” *Journal of Neuroscience*, vol. 31, no. 12, pp. 4475–4483, 2011. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.5725-10.2011>.
- [49] B. Stoffel-Wagner, “Neurosteroid metabolism in the human brain,” *European Journal of Endocrinology*, vol. 145, no. 6, pp. 669–679, 2001. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1530/eje.0.1450669>.
- [50] L. Cui *et al.*, “Major depressive disorder: hypothesis, mechanism, prevention and treatment,” *Signal Transduction and Targeted Therapy*, vol. 9, p. 30, 2024. doi: [10.1038/s41392-024-01738-y](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41392-024-01738-y).
- [51] D. A. Gutman and C. B. Nemeroff, “Stress and depression,” in *The Handbook of Stress Science: Biology, Psychology, and Health*, 2011, pp. 345–357.
- [52] V. Krishnan and E. J. Nestler, “The molecular neurobiology of depression,” *Nature*, vol. 455, no. 7215, pp. 894–902, 2008. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature07455>.
- [53] S. Chourbaji *et al.*, “Learned helplessness: validity and reliability of depressive-like states in mice,” *Brain Research Protocols*, vol. 16, no. 1–3, pp. 70–78, 2005. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.brainresprot.2005.09.002>.
- [54] J. A. Gray and B. Lalljee, “Sex differences in emotional behaviour in the rat: correlation between open-field defecation and active avoidance,” *Animal Behaviour*, vol. 22, pp. 856–861, 1974. doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0003-3472\(74\)90008-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0003-3472(74)90008-6).
- [55] C. McGrath and T. R. Norman, “(+)-S-20499—a potential antidepressant? A behavioural and neurochemical investigation in the olfactory bulbectomised rat,” *European Neuropsychopharmacology*, vol. 9, no. 1–2, pp. 21–27, 1999. doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0924-977X\(97\)00103-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0924-977X(97)00103-X).
- [56] C. Chourpiliadis *et al.*, “Metabolic profile and long-term risk of depression, anxiety, and stress-related disorders,” *JAMA Network Open*, 2024. doi: [10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2024.4525](https://doi.org/10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2024.4525).
- [57] T. Tong *et al.*, “Electroacupuncture ameliorates chronic unpredictable mild stress-induced depression-like behavior and cognitive impairment through suppressing oxidative stress and neuroinflammation in rats,” *Brain Research Bulletin*, vol. 206, p. 110838, 2024. doi: [10.1016/j.brainresbull.2023.110838](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.brainresbull.2023.110838).
- [58] C. Song and B. E. Leonard, “The olfactory bulbectomised rat as a model of depression,” *Neuroscience and Biobehavioral Reviews*, vol. 29, no. 4–5, pp. 627–647, 2005. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neubiorev.2005.03.010>.
- [59] G. Vitale *et al.*, “Chronic treatment with the selective NOP receptor antagonist [Nphe¹, Arg¹⁴, Lys¹⁵] N/OFQ-NH₂ (UFP-101) reverses the behavioural and biochemical effects of unpredictable chronic mild stress in rats,” *Psychopharmacology*, vol. 207, pp. 173–189, 2009. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00213-009-1646-9>.
- [60] B. S. McEwen, “Non-genomic and genomic effects of steroids on neural activity,” *Trends in Pharmacological Sciences*, vol. 12, pp. 141–147, 1991. doi: [10.1016/0165-6147\(91\)90531-V](https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-6147(91)90531-V).
- [61] D. S. Charney, “Monoamine dysfunction and the pathophysiology and treatment of depression,” *Journal of Clinical Psychiatry*, vol. 59, no. 14, pp. 11–14, 1998.
- [62] B. Czeh, E. Fuchs, O. Wiborg, and M. Simon, “Animal models of major depression and their clinical implications,” *Progress in Neuro-Psychopharmacology and Biological Psychiatry*, vol. 64, pp. 293–310, 2016. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pnpbp.2015.04.004>.
- [63] R. Dantzer *et al.*, “From inflammation to sickness and depression: when the immune system subjugates the brain,” *Nature Reviews Neuroscience*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 46–56, 2008. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrn2297>.
- [64] L. M. Telega *et al.*, “Reserpine-induced rat model for depression: behavioral, physiological and PET-based dopamine receptor availability validation,” *Progress in Neuropsychopharmacology and Biological Psychiatry*, vol. 133, p. 111013, 2024. doi: [10.1016/j.pnpbp.2024.111013](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pnpbp.2024.111013).
- [65] P. E. Simson and J. M. Weiss, “Altered activity of the locus coeruleus in an animal model of depression,” *Neuropsychopharmacology*, vol. 1, pp. 287–295, 1988.
- [66] M. Govindarajulu *et al.*, “Reserpine-induced depression and other neurotoxicity: A monoaminergic hypothesis,” in *Medicinal Herbs and Fungi: Neurotoxicity vs. Neuroprotection*, 2021, pp. 293–313. doi: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-33-4141-8_12.
- [67] S. L. Gourley and J. R. Taylor, “Recapitulation and reversal of a persistent depression-like syndrome in rodents,” *Current Protocols in Neuroscience*, vol. 49, no. 1, pp. 9–32, 2009. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/0471142301.ns0932s49>.

- [68] S. F. Maier and M. E. P. Seligman, "Learned helplessness at fifty: Insights from neuroscience," *Psychological Review*, 2016. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1037/rev0000033>.
- [69] S. A. El-Marasy *et al.*, "Anti-depressant effect of cerebrolysin in reserpine-induced depression in rats: Behavioral, biochemical, molecular and immunohistochemical evidence," *Chemico-Biological Interactions*, vol. 334, p. 109329, 2021. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cbi.2020.109329>.
- [70] K. Sanmugam, "Depression is a Risk Factor for Alzheimer Disease - Review," *Research J. Pharm. and Tech.*, vol. 8, no. 8, pp. 1056–1058, 2015. doi: 10.5958/0974-360X.2015.00181.X.